

Further Studies on the Chemical Behaviour of Vitamin B₂.

BY B. C. GUHA AND P. N. CHAKRAVORTY.

Researches on the chemistry of vitamin B₂, which have been reported earlier (Guha, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 945 ; Guha and Chakravorty, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1933, 21, 211), have shown that vitamin B₂ is chemically very different from vitamin B₁. Whereas vitamin B₁ behaved like a fairly strong base in electrolysis experiments (Birch and Guha, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 1391) vitamin B₂ had obviously no basic properties (Guha, *loc. cit.*). It was observed that vitamin B₂ was precipitated or carried down by several metallic precipitants like lead acetate and silver nitrate. Some further investigations on the chemical behaviour of vitamin B₂ are reported in the present communication. Although it was found earlier by most workers (Narayanan and Drummond, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 24, 19 ; Salmon, Guerrant and Hays, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 80, 91) that the vitamin was efficiently adsorbed but not easily eluted, we have recently succeeded in eluting the vitamin by means of suitable solvents. It may be mentioned that in view of the recent work on the relative instability of the vitamin in certain preparations to heat and alkali (Guha and Chakravorty, *loc. cit.*), procedures involving any heat treatment with alkali have been avoided in this work. The biological technique followed has been the same as described before (Guha and Chakravorty, *loc. cit.*). During the progress of this work Kuhn, György and Wagner-Jauregg (*Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 1034) reported that vitamin B₂ belonged to a new class of natural pigments for which the term "flavin" has been employed. Only subsequent research can determine the correctness of Kuhn's contention (*cf.* also Ellinger and Koschara, *Ber.*, 1933, 66 B, 808). Our results in many cases agree with those of Kuhn.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following results were obtained chiefly with ox and buffalo liver and kidney extracts, which had been found to be very potent sources of vitamin B₂ (Guha, *loc. cit.* ; Guha and Chakravorty, *loc. cit.*).

The technique for the assay of the vitamin in different fractions was essentially the same as described before (Guha and Chakravorty,

loc. cit.). We have used the unit, previously defined (Guha and Chakravorty, *loc. cit.*), which is very similar to that proposed earlier by Bourquin and Sherman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 3501).

From earlier observations (Guha, *loc. cit.*) it was known that vitamin B₂ could be adsorbed by charcoal although elution could not be effected. It was thought that the adsorption might be optimum at a specific hydrogen ion concentration and accordingly the following observations were made.

Effect of pH on Adsorption of Vitamin B₂ on Charcoal.

TABLE I.

Samples No.	Adsorption at diff. pH.	No. of rats	Equiv. daily doses.	Average weekly growth.
O.L. (158)	Glacial HAc ext ₂ of charcoal adsorbate	385	16 g.	10 g.
O.L. (160)		365	12	
O.L. (162))		364	12	3
O.L. (164)		366	8	4
O.L. (168)		378	8	-4
O.L. (170)		458	8	3
O.L. (157)	Filtrate from adsorption	414	4.5	9
O.L. (159)		397	6	5.6
O.L. (161)	
O.L. (163)		378	5.2	-1
O.L. (167)		378	5	-2
O.L. (169)		394	5	1
O.L. (153)	Crude liver extract used in this set of experiments	396	1.76	17.3

Six lots of crude liver extract of 220 c.c. each (\equiv 200 g. of fresh liver), obtained by boiling ox-liver (5760 g.) with distilled water (6500 c.c.) for 6 minutes, were respectively adjusted to pH 1.2, 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0 and 11.0. Each lot was then agitated with purified * Merck's

* 100 G. of charcoal were digested for 30 hours over a flame with 1 litre of 50% hydrochloric acid. The acid was decanted off and the charcoal was washed chloride-free with distilled water. This purified charcoal was used throughout the experiments.

medicinal charcoal (8 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, filtered under suction and the filtrate was again agitated with charcoal (4 g.) for 15 minutes. The mixture was filtered on the same filter paper. The filtrate was stored in the refrigerator.

Each lot of the charcoal residue was ground up with glacial acetic acid (15-20 c. c.) and then digested for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on a boiling water-bath with a further amount of the acid. The total volume of acid used was 100 c. c. in each case. The mixture was then filtered hot under suction, the clear filtrate evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in warm water.

The extent of adsorption at the different hydrogen ion concentrations and the amounts of vitamin eluted are given in Table I. (cf. also Fig. 1).

It appears from the results in Table I that the adsorption of vitamin B₂ is not complete at any definite pH.

FIG. 1. (cf. Table I.)

Curve (1)	Rat No. 385 (female)	Fraction No. O.	L. (158)
(2)	396 (male)	" "	(153)
(3)	366 (")	" "	(161)
(4)	364 (")	" "	(162)
(5)	378 (female)	" "	(168)
(6)	365 "	" "	(160)
(7)	414 "	" "	(157)

The Efficiency of Different Extractants in Eluting Vitamin B₂ from Charcoal Adsorbate.

880 C. c. O. L. (153), a crude liver-extract (\cong 800 g. of fresh liver) were brought to pH 7.0. 48 G. of purified Merck's medicinal charcoal were agitated with the extract for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. This was filtered under suction and the filtrate was kept in the refrigerator [O. L. (171)].

The finely ground charcoal residue was divided into four equal parts and treated as follows:

(a) *Elution with methyl alcohol.*—One portion (\cong 200 g. of fresh liver) of the residue was heated under reflux for 1 hour on a water-bath with methyl alcohol (250 c. c.) (Merck's "methanol purum"). The mixture was filtered hot under suction and the charcoal washed with a little methyl alcohol. The filtrate was almost colourless. The clear filtrate was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo* and the brown-red residue dissolved in warm water [O.L.(172)].

(b) *Elution with methyl alcohol and hydrochloric acid.*—Another portion (\cong 200 g. fresh liver) of the residue was similarly heated with methyl alcohol (250 c. c.) and concentrated HCl (5 c. c.), filtered hot under suction and the charcoal washed with a little methyl alcohol. The pale-brown filtrate was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The dark brown pasty mass was dissolved in warm water [O L.(173)].

(c) *Elution with 1% hydrochloric acid.*—One portion (\cong 200 g. fresh liver) of the adsorbate was digested on a boiling water-bath for 45 minutes with 1% HCl (100 c.c.). The mixture was filtered hot under suction and the colourless filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The dark-brown residue was taken up in warm water [O. L. (174)].

(d) *Elution with glacial acetic acid.*—One portion (\cong 200 g. fresh liver) of the residue was digested for 1 hour on a boiling water-bath with glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.). The mixture was filtered under suction and the pale brown filtrate evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The dark-brown residue was taken up in warm water [O. L.(175)].

In another set of experiment 750 c.c. of O. L. (153), a crude aqueous extract of liver (\cong 681 g. of fresh liver) were brought to pH 7.0, agitated with Merck's purified medicinal charcoal (24 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and filtered under suction. The charcoal residue was divided into three portions and was treated as follows.

(e) *Elution with pyridine.*—A part of the charcoal residue (\cong 227 g. fresh liver) was digested at room temperature (29°) with

100 c.c. of pyridine, stirring continually for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After filtering under suction, pyridine was distilled off *in vacuo* and the residue obtained was dissolved in warm water [O. L. (178)].

(f) *Elution with glacial acetic acid.*—A part of the charcoal residue (\equiv 227 g. fresh liver) was digested on a boiling water-bath with glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After removing charcoal by hot filtration, the clear yellow filtrate was evaporated *in vacuo* to dryness and the residue obtained was taken up in warm water [O.L. (179)].

FIG. 2 (cf. Table II).

Curve	Rat. No.	Sex	Fraction No.	O. L.	Weight
(1)	396	male		(153)	
(2)	312	(")	"	"	(126)
(3)	420	(")	"	"	(178)
(4)	393	female	"	"	(174)
(5)	390	(")	"	"	(173)
(6)	418	(")	"	"	(178)
(7)	419	(")	"	"	(179)
(8)	380	(")	"	"	(172)
(9)	399	(")	"	"	(171)

(g) *Elution with 25% pyridine.*—A portion of the charcoal was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 1½ hour with pyridine (260 c.c., 25%). After filtering hot under suction, the filtrate was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The residue obtained was taken up in water [O. L. (126)].

(h) *Elution with conc. HCl.*—The experiment was carried out on a fresh lot of liver extract. 220 C.c. of O. L. (153) (\equiv 200 g. ox-liver) were brought to pH 7.0 and agitated with purified charcoal (8 g.) for ½ hour and filtered under suction. The charcoal residue was ground up with concentrated HCl (10 c.c.) and then with 80 c.c. of water. This was boiled over a flame for 1-2 minutes and filtered hot under suction. The colourless dark filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in water [O. L. (189)].

Table II summarises the results obtained (*cf.* Fig. 2). Methyl alcohol with hydrochloric acid appears to be the most efficient agent for the elution of the vitamin, while methyl alcohol by itself could not extract vitamin B₂. Other extractants have varying capacities to elute the vitamin.

TABLE II.

Samples No.	Efficiency of different elutants. Descriptions.	No. of rat.	Equivalent daily dose.	Average weekly growth.
O. L. (171)	Filtrate after charcoal ad- sorption for elution expts.	399	5 g.	2.5 g.
O. L. (172)	Elution with MeOH	380	16	-3
O. L. (173)	„ „ MeOH + HCl	390	8	11.5
O. L. (174)	„ „ 1% HCl	393	8	6
O. L. (175)	„ „ glacial acetic acid	459	10	6
O. L. (178)	„ „ absolute pyridine (digestion)	418	9	6
„ „	„ „ „ „	420	13.6	16
O. L. (179)	„ glacial acetic acid	419	9	7
O. L. (180)	„ 1% „ „	417	9.8	-2
O. L. (126)	„ „ 25% pyridine re- fluxing	312	8	4
O. L. (153)	Crude liver extract used in this set of experiments	396	1.76	17.3
O. L. (189)	Elution with conc. HCl	391	13	2

Further Adsorption Experiments.

Vitamin B₂ has been reported to be adsorbed by various substances such as charcoal (Guha, *loc. cit.*), fuller's earth (Narayanan and Drummond, *loc. cit.*) etc. In order to investigate the optimum conditions for adsorption and elution the following experiments were carried out.

(a) *Adsorption with fuller's earth.*—140 C.c. of B. L. (7), a crude aqueous extract of buffalo-liver (\equiv 140 g. of fresh liver) were found to be at pH 5.0. The extract was stirred with 5 g. of Merck's fuller's earth for 15 minutes and filtered. The filtrate was tested for activity [B.L. (10)].

The fuller's earth residue was triturated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) whereupon some evolution of CO₂ took place. This was then diluted to 75 c.c. and boiled over an open flame for 2 minutes. The extracted residue was separated by filtration and the yellow filtrate was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The residue, thus obtained, was taken up in warm water, neutralised and the precipitate obtained at that stage removed and the orange-red filtrate tested for activity [B. L. (13)].

In another experiment 100 c.c. of O.L. (68), a crude aqueous ox-liver extract (\equiv 110 g. fresh liver) were adjusted to pH 4.5 and stirred with Merck's Fuller's earth (5 g.) for 20 minutes and filtered under suction. The filtrate was tested [O. L. 77)].

The residue was dried in the steam oven at 50° and powdered. The powder was stored at -1° for 15 days and then tested for activity. The earth was suspended in water and tested [O. L. (81)].

(b) *Adsorption with charcoal and elution with HCl.*—140 C.c. of B.L. (7), a crude aqueous extract of buffalo-liver, (\equiv 100 g. fresh liver) were agitated with purified Merck's medicinal charcoal (5 g.) for 15 minutes. After separating the charcoal residue, the filtrate [B.L. (11)] was tested for any vitamin left after adsorption.

The charcoal residue was boiled over a flame with water (50 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) for 3-4 minutes. The extracted residue was separated and the filtrate evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The residue obtained was taken up in water [B.L. (14)].

The extracted charcoal residue [B.L. (15)] was also tested for residual vitamin activity.

(c) *Adsorption with silica gel.*—200 C.c. of O. K. (11), a crude aqueous extract of ox-kidney, (\equiv 80 g. of fresh kidney) were treated

with 10 g. of silica gel for 10-12 minutes and the silica residue separated by filtration under suction. The pale yellowish filtrate was numbered O.K. (13).

The silica residue was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) (large excess) and water (50 c.c.) over an open flame for 5 minutes and filtered under suction. The clear pale yellow filtrate was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The dark brown residue was taken up in warm water. O.K. (14).

FIG. 3 (cf. TABLE III).

Curve (1)	Rat. No. 114 (female)	Fraction No. B.L. (11)
(2)	" 140 (male)	" O.K. (14)
(3)	" 274 (")	" O.L. (81)
(4)	" 306 (")	" O.L. (77)
(5)	" 85 (")	" B.L. (11)
(6)	" 89 (female)	" B.L. (14)
(7)	" 90 (male)	" B.L. (15)

Silica-gel appears to adsorb vitamin B₂ efficiently, and elution could be effected by boiling with strong hydrochloric acid.

(d) *Adsorption with barium sulphate.*—35 C.c. of O.L. (38), an active extract which was prepared by a method similar to that employed for O.L. (47), (\approx 735 g. fresh liver), were brought to pH 9.0, by adding saturated baryta (25 c.c.) whereupon a small amount of precipitate was formed. A few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ were added without removing the precipitate and the pH was found to have come down to 6.0. The precipitate was allowed to settle overnight in the cold store. The barium precipitate was removed by centrifugation. The centrifugate was numbered O.L. (44).

The precipitate was boiled up for a minute with concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) and 4 drops of concentrated H₂SO₄, diluted with water (15 c.c.). The residue was removed and the filtrate partly neutralised by 20% NaOH. A dark brown precipitate, which came down at this stage, was removed by centrifugation. The dark brown centrifugate was called O. L. (45).

The vitamin could not be found either in the filtrate or in the residue.

TABLE III.

No. of Samples.	Description	No. of Rat.	Equivalent daily dose.	Average weekly growth.
B. L. (10)	Filtrate from F. E. adsorption at pH 5.0	109	4.2 g.	1.3 g.
B. L. (13)	HCl-ext. of F. E. adsorbate	84	4	-5
O. L. (77)	Filtrate from F. E. adsorption at pH 4.5	306	5.8	4.8
O. L. (81)	F. E. adsorbate, dried and stored in the cold	274	8.3	Inactive
B. L. (11)	Filtrate from charcoal adsorption at pH 7.0	85	4	5
B. L. (14)	HCl-ext. of charcoal adsorbate	86	4	7
" "	" " "	89	4	11
" "	" " "	114	3	5
B. L. (15)	HCl extracted charcoal residue	90	4	-9
O. K. (13)	Filtrate from Si-gel adsorption	132	3.2	Inactive
O. K. (14)	HCl-extract of Si-gel adsorbate	140	4	6.5
O. L. (44)	Filtrate from BaSO ₄ -pptn.	181	7.4	Inactive
O. L. (45)	HCl-extract of BaSO ₄	180	18	Inactive

Fractionation Studies.

With a view to fractionating vitamin B₂ its behaviour to certain precipitants, both metallic and organic, was studied.

(a) *Precipitation with cupric acetate.*—280 C.c. of B.L. (7) a crude buffalo liver extract (\equiv 200 g. of fresh liver), were treated with about 100 c.c. of saturated cupric acetate solution. A precipitate began to come down and precipitation was complete after boiling for about $\frac{1}{2}$ min. The greenish precipitate was removed by filtration under suction.

The filtrate was completely freed from copper by passing H₂S and from the latter by heating the filtrate on a water-bath *in vacuo* [B.L. (8)].

The filtrate was active while no activity could be traced in the precipitate fraction.

(b) *Fractionation with mercuric chloride.*—10 C.c. of O. L. (47), an active extract of liver obtained after the silver-stage (\equiv 470 g. of fresh ox liver), were treated with 0.5N-HgCl₂ solution (2.2 c.c.) whereupon a small amount of precipitate came down. After allowing the precipitate to settle in cold store, the precipitate (A) was removed by centrifugation. The clear filtrate was freed from mercury as sulphide (B) by passing H₂S and the latter was removed by evaporating the liquid to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂ and soda lime. The small residue thus obtained was taken up in warm water [O. L. (52)].

The microcrystalline precipitate (A), which was chocolate coloured, was decomposed by H₂S and the sulphide removed. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂ and soda lime and the residue obtained was taken up in water [O.L. (54)].

The sulphide precipitate (B) was boiled for 2 minutes over a flame with HCl about 8 c.c. of 25%. After filtering hot under suction the clear filtrate was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was extracted with warm water and the mixture was filtered hot. The clear yellowish filtrate was called O.L. (53).

In another set of experiments 15 c.c. of O.L. (59) were treated with about HgCl₂ solution (6 c. c. of 5.8 %). A slight opalescence took place. Without removing the precipitate H₂S was passed till mercury was completely precipitated. The precipitate (A) was separated by filtration and the lemon-yellow filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂ and soda lime. The residue was then taken up in water. [O.L. (62)]

The HgS precipitate (A) was extracted with boiling 25% HCl (25 c.c.) and filtered hot. The extract was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the residue was taken up in warm water [O.L. (63)].

The action of HgCl₂ appears to be similar to that of barium inasmuch as no activity could be found either in the HgCl₂ precipitate or in the filtrate left.

(c) *Experiments with bromine.*—120 C.c. O.L. (18) (\equiv 100 g. fresh ox liver) were shaken with 25 c.c. bromine. A flocculent precipitate came down and was removed by filtering under suction. The filtrate was red owing to excess of bromine being present. It was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*, and the residue thus obtained was taken up in warm water [O.L. (20)].

It appears that vitamin B₂ is stable to bromine.

(d) *Experiments with silver nitrate after bromination.*—From a few preliminary experiments meant to ascertain whether vitamin B₂ came down with the silver precipitate fraction after bromination or it remained dissolved in the filtrate, it was found that vitamin B₂ associated itself with the AgBr precipitate in course of precipitation. This observation is in agreement with the earlier work of Guha (*loc. cit.*).

A suitable means of elution of the vitamin from this precipitate having been found the following experiment was carried out.

Eight litres of crude liver extract (7,500 g. of fresh liver) were brominated by adding about 13 c.c. of bromine with vigorous shaking. After allowing the precipitate to settle, the clear reddish supernatant liquid was syphoned off.

The liquid was treated with about 250 c.c. of 50% AgNO₃ solution and was left overnight for allowing the precipitate to settle.

The silver precipitate (180 g.) obtained by syphoning off the clear supernatant liquid and by subsequent filtration, was ground up with concentrated hydrochloric acid (65 c.c.) and then diluted with about 500 c.c. of water. The mixture was boiled over an open flame for 6 minutes and filtered hot under suction.

The clear red filtrate was freed from the acid by evaporation to dryness *in vacuo*. The residue was dissolved in warm water and the opalescent liquid was left overnight in the refrigerator. A dark brown precipitate came down and was removed by filtration under suction. [O.L. (47)].

Solvent Fractionation Methods.

Attempts were made to concentrate vitamin B₂ by means of fractionation with solvents, as described in the following experiments.

(a) *Fractional precipitation with EtOH.*—70 C.c. of O. L. (47), a concentrate of vitamin B₂ from ox-liver (\equiv 3281 g. of fresh liver), were evaporated to a small volume (10-12 c.c.) on a water-bath. On adding about 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol an immediate precipitation took place. After cooling down to 0°, the precipitate (A) was removed by centrifugation. The centrifugate, which was opalescent, was further treated by an equal volume (70—75 c.c.) of absolute alcohol, whereby further precipitation took place. The residue (B) was removed by centrifuging. The clear centrifugate, after adding some more alcohol, was left in the refrigerator and after 6 days precipitate (C) appeared and was separated by centrifugation. The clear centrifugate was freed from alcohol by evaporating to dryness *in vacuo* and the black-brown residue obtained was taken up in warm water. This did not dissolve entirely. [O.L. (50).]

The precipitates (A) and (B) were mixed together and dried in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂ and soda lime. The dried residue, which was reddish brown, did not dissolve in water. This was fed in aqueous suspension [O.L. (48)].

The precipitate (C) was also dried in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂ and soda lime. The dried residue was a light yellowish brown powder which dissolved in water giving a dark brown solution with green fluorescence [O.L. (49)].

(b) *Precipitation with MeOH.*—25 C.c. of B.L. (55) (\equiv 116 g. of fresh buffalo liver), were treated with methyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and left in the refrigerator. The precipitate formed was separated by filtration and dried and was found to be very hygroscopic. The dried residue could not be entirely dissolved in boiling water [B.L. (56)].

The filtrate was concentrated on a water-bath to remove methyl alcohol and was tested for vitamin B₂ activity. [B.L. (60).]

The methyl alcohol filtrate had no activity, while the residue was active.

(c) *Precipitation with propyl alcohol.*—20 C.c. of B.L. (55) (\equiv 116 g. fresh buffalo liver) were treated with *n*-propyl alcohol (4 c.c.) and a gummy precipitate obtained. The clear supernatant liquid was removed by decantation and the washed residue was dried

in vacuum desiccator over CaCl₂ and soda-lime. The dried residue was taken up in hot water [B.L. (58)].

The washings and the supernatant liquid from the above fraction were combined and were freed from alcohol by evaporating to a small volume on a water-bath. The fraction was tested for activity. [B.L. (61)].

FIG. 4 (cf. TABLE IV)

Curve (1)	Rat. No. 183 (female)	Fraction No. O.L. (47)
(2)	" 175 (")	" " (47)
(3)	" 182 (male)	" " (50)
(4)	" 74 (female)	" B.L. (8)
(5)	" 274 (male)	" O.L. (53)
(6)	" 269 (")	" B.L. (61)
(7)	" 194 (female)	" B.L. (55)

It is curious to note that no activity could be found either in the propyl alcohol filtrate or in the residue. No growth was observed even when both the residue and filtrate were fed together.

Testing Known Substances for Vitamin B₂ Activity.

Following substances were tested for vitamin B₂ activity with negative results. The daily dose is given in brackets.

Arabinose (1 mg.), xylose (1 mg.), galactose (1 mg.), arabinose + xylose (1 mg. each), arabinose + galactose (1 mg. each), irradiated adenine (5 mg.), irradiated guanine (5 mg.), cytosine (5g.).

TABLE IV.

Samples No.	Description.	No of Rat.	Eqiuv. daily dose	Average weekly growth.
B. L. (8)	Filtrate from CuAc ₂ -pptn	94	10 g.	8 g.
O. L. (52)	Filtrate from HgCl ₂ -pptn of O. L. (47) ...	269	18·8	1
O. L. (54)	Extract of HgCl ₂ .ppt. ...	270	18·8	0
O. L. (53)	Extract of HgS obtained from O. L. (52) ...	274	14·1	0
O. L. (62)	Filtrate from HgCl ₂ -treated fraction ...	268	12·8	Inactive
O. L. (63)	HgS extract ...	273	19·3	Inactive
O. L. (20)	Br ₂ treated liver extract ...	180	3	2·7
O. L. (47)	Ag extract after bromine treatment ...	175	14	9·3
"	" " " "	180	10	4·7
"	" " " "	183	10	12·5
O. L. (50)	Centrifugate after EtOH -pptn.	182	32·8	8·7
O. L. (48)	The first fraction precipitated by alcohol ...	186	32·8	8
O. L. (49)	The second " " "	185	32·8	5·3
"	" " " "	178	16·4	2·7
B. L. (56)	Residue from MeOH-treated B.L. (55) ...	270	8·8	9·3
B. L. (60)	Filtrate from MeOH-treated B. L. (55) ...	268	9·3	Inactive
B. L. (58)	Residue from propyl alcohol fractionation ...	269	9·3	-8
B. L. (61)	Filtrate from propyl alcohol fractionation ...	269	14·5	Inactive
B. L. (61) } B. L. (58) }	Propyl alcohol residue and filtrate ...	269	7·25 of filtrate and 4·6 of residue	Inactive
B. L. (55)	Desiccated buffalo liver extract	194	2·9	7

DISCUSSION.

The results described in this paper indicate that most metallic fractionations cause a very considerable loss of vitamin B₂ probably owing to adsorption on the surface of the various precipitates formed. Results obtained are better with methyl alcohol, although in solvent fractionation methods also a satisfactory recovery of activity is not usually possible. The adsorption experiments, if further pursued, are likely to give greater scope for successful concentration. Adsorption on charcoal and elution with methyl alcohol and hydrochloric acid constitute one of the most effective methods for concentration so far discovered.

The procedure, which has given consistently good results, consists of bromination (which causes no loss), adsorption with silver bromide and elution with hydrochloric acid, followed by adsorption methods.

It is not possible yet to postulate the nature of the vitamin B₂ molecule. Our experience indicates, that it is not at all so stable as it was originally supposed to be. The precipitation of the vitamin by silver nitrate and lead acetate (Guha, *loc. cit.*) might indicate either that the vitamin is acidic or that it is neutral and is adsorbed by the metallic precipitates formed. It has been pointed out before (Guha, *loc. cit.*) that it cannot be of the nature of a base.

The remarkable stability of the vitamin to bromine appears to indicate that the activity is not associated with any unsaturated linkage in the molecule.

SUMMARY.

1. The adsorption of vitamin B₂ on charcoal at p_H 1.2, 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 9.0, and 11.0 was studied. No high degree of specificity was observed at any of the above hydrogen ion concentrations under the stated conditions.

2. Methyl alcohol with HCl, absolute methyl alcohol, 1% HCl, glacial acetic acid, absolute pyridine, 25% pyridine and strong hydrochloric acid were tried to elute vitamin B₂ from the charcoal adsorbate. Methyl alcohol with hydrochloric acid and pyridine were found to be the most efficient of all the extractants used. Methyl alcohol by itself could not elute the vitamin.

3. Vitamin B₂ could be apparently adsorbed by fuller's earth, charcoal, silica gel and freshly precipitated barium sulphate. While the vitamin could be eluted from the charcoal and silica gel adsorbates, the methods employed were not found so suitable for the elution of the vitamin from fuller's earth or barium.

4. Bromine could neither precipitate nor destroy the vitamin to any appreciable extent. Silver either forms an insoluble compound with vitamin B₂ or silver bromide can adsorb it. The vitamin could not be concentrated by means of HgCl₂ or propyl alcohol. Ethyl alcohol can fractionally precipitate the vitamin. Methyl alcohol forms a precipitate which contains most of the activity.

5. Sugars like arabinose, xylose and galactose, administered singly or in combination with one another, could not replace vitamin B₂ in the diet. Irradiated adenine, guanine, cytosine and nucleic acid have no vitamin B₂ activity.

BIOCHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BENGAL CHEMICAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL
WORKS, CALCUTTA.

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